

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

DEVELOPING LISTENING SKILLS IN NON-LINGUISTIC HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Moshynska O.

*Candidate of Philosophical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Yaroslav Mudryi National Law University,
Kharkiv, Ukraine*

Abstract

The great attention of researchers to the issue of listening is conditioned by the fact that the training of speech reception by ear has been and continues to be an important direction of foreign language teaching methodology. Training of semantic receptive speech listening both in domestic and foreign methodological science of foreign language teaching is given the most serious attention. Listening as one of the numerous processes of communication by means of language forms the mentality of an individual, influencing his mind, feelings and intents through the content of the meaning of what is communicated. This is one of the main reasons why foreign language teaching assumes as its goal the formation of skills and abilities of so-called mature listening.

Keywords: listening, pre-textual exercises, intra-auditory exercises, post-auditory tasks, speaking, vocabulary, authentic speech.

The concept of “listening” was introduced by Donn Byrne in his work “Teaching Oral English”. Listening is the ability to understand and distinguish what is spoken by others, and when applied to the learning process in foreign language classes, it is listening comprehension of foreign language speech while it is being spoken.

The origins of communicative language teaching lie in the changes in the British language teaching tradition since the late 1960s. In the same period, the main directions of studying this problem were identified, which were further developed in the works of psychologists, philologists and teachers. Four directions that are most relevant in teaching listening to foreign-language speech were identified: the study of psycho-levels and psychomechanisms of reception and understanding of speech; checking the extent to which the skills and abilities of audio perception and interpretation of speech are formed; methods of overcoming linguistic and extra-linguistic difficulties of listening; study of audio materials and methods of their rational use.

In order to purposefully overcome difficulties in teaching listening, it is necessary to present their types and classification.

1. Difficulties related to the peculiarities of listening as a type of speech activity and the conditions in which this activity is carried out.

1.1 One-time and short-term presentation of information, which requires the listener to react quickly.

1.2 The pace of the speaker's speech, which makes the listener perceive the speech in a certain “speed mode”.

1.3 The need to adapt to different vocal characteristics and individual manner of pronunciation.

2 Difficulties arising from the linguistic features of the material being listened to can be phonetic, lexical and grammatical.

2.1 Phonetic difficulties: the difference in the phonetic structure of the native and foreign languages; difficulties in recognising a word due to the discrepancy between its spelling and pronunciation.

2.2 Lexical difficulties: difficulties caused by recognising homophones, homonyms, distinguishing lexical and semantic variants of polysemantic words; the presence of words that are difficult to understand: numerals, terms, etc.; difficulties caused by the wide use of word formation methods (word combinations, conversions, abbreviations).

2.3 Grammatical difficulties: difficulties caused by differences in the structure of the target and native languages; difficulties related to the polysemous nature of many grammatical phenomena, e.g. temporal forms.

3. Difficulties related to the semantic processing of the material.

3.1 Associating verbal information with visual support in the form of diagrams, charts, graphs, formulas, etc.

3.2 Listening comprehension of text without visual supports in the form of diagrams, charts, graphs, drawings, pictures.

3.3 The misunderstanding of individual words can often lead to the fact that students, thinking about the meaning of a single word, may not hear the whole phrase and thus lose the thread and stop listening further.

In the learning process, listening can act not only as an end but also as a means. For example, in the role of: 1) a mechanism for organising the learning process; 2) a way of introducing language material in verbal form; 3) a method of teaching other types of speech communication; 4) a means of controlling acquired knowledge, skills and abilities.

Three stages of work on listening are distinguished: 1) the pre-textual stage (before listening); 2) the stage of own listening (while listening); 3) the post-textual stage (Follow-up activities). Accordingly, it is reasonable to divide the exercises used when working with an audio text into the following groups: 1) pre-textual exercises; 2) exercises performed during listening; 3) post-textual exercises.

Pre-textual exercises are done before listening and their purpose is to facilitate subsequent listening. They

can be exercises to anticipate the topic of the future listening (e.g. pictures, title of the topic, diagrams). The purpose of such exercises is to activate the students' vocabulary on the given topic, to develop their socio-cultural situational knowledge and background skills on the listening topic, as well as to level out linguistic and extra-linguistic difficulties and psycho-emotional tension.

Intra-auditory exercises are mainly aimed at extracting information of interest to the communicator. They often test the student's ability to navigate in the text, to realise in which part of it to look for the necessary information, to correlate visually and auditorily perceived information, to find the necessary element as quickly as possible. Often such tasks are given in the form of 'blank gaps', for example, in the form of filling in gaps in the text or a table.

Post-auditory tasks are often of a controlling nature (e.g. answering questions or true/false exercises). They reveal the ability to express one's attitude to what has been listened to, the level of understanding of the information contained in the text, the degree of understanding of the details and general content of the text.

It is very important, when starting work on an audio text, to create a situation of success for the learner, i.e. to offer him/her a task that is obviously realistic to fulfil. Excessively difficult texts can lead to frustration and discourage learners from believing in the results they can achieve. Excessively easy audio texts are also not very desirable. The absence of the need to overcome difficulties makes the work on the text uninteresting and unattractive, such work can not be a developing factor in the process of teaching a foreign language.

Speaking about listening strategies, it is necessary to pay attention to the increase of students' motivation to learn a foreign language, because it is the quality of implementation of listening and the result of such activity depends mainly on the intensions, requests and needs of the audience. It is necessary to pay attention to the decrease of motivation in students of non-language university to learn a foreign language. It is necessary to comprehend as deeply as possible the issue of increasing the motivation for learning a foreign language in students of non-language universities.

The first aspect that can be successfully developed through listening is phonetics.

Also listening allows practising vocabulary. Here it is worth mentioning the use of spot listening (filling in the blanks while listening). This type of tasks trains spelling skills and allows students to empirically grasp the morphological and morphemic mechanisms of language.

It is possible to combine it with a grammatical component, when different grammatical forms are omitted in the text offered by the learner. Within this type of listening it is possible to use not only complete text constructions, dialogues and other, but also songs in the target language. It is also justified to use situational-thematic listening when learning situational vocabulary, for example, in pre-textual tasks on a topic (students are offered pictures, by which they should identify the situation, actors, etc., and then offered to

listen to a text or dialogue on this or that topic with subsequent performance of post-textual tasks: to compose a message on the topic, dialogue, etc.).

It is important to note that the materials that are offered in listening classes should be mostly original. This is due to the fact that teaching a modern and maximally natural foreign language is realistic only when using materials that are taken from the life of native speakers or compiled, taking into account the specificity of mentality, in accordance with the language norms accepted in the society.

If the aim of the lesson is to develop grammatical skills, original speech can be a way of recognising in the text, for example, the use of the verb tense studied in a particular lesson.

Speaking about the vocabulary-forming purpose of the lesson, it is worth noting that authentic speech can help to master and consolidate new vocabulary. As for phonetic skills, it is important to pay attention to the learner's identification of the intonation pattern of a phrase, to how one can master the technique of foreign-language sound representation.

It is important to note that improving the mechanism of foreign language speech reception in students of non-linguistic higher education is a very serious aspect of learning, because within the framework of higher education the volume and complexity of auditable foreign-language information, including that affecting the professional aspect, is increasing.

Students of non-philological universities need to involve specific cognitive reactions: analysis, identification, combination, as well as to improve the mechanism of listening, because on its basis the skills and abilities are formed and developed, which are necessary in order to implement the strategy of semantic reception. And this can be facilitated by autonomous and independent work of students.

Thus, it is possible to identify those types of listening that are most demanded by students of non-language universities: listening with maximum detailed reception of the message; listening with understanding of the general orientation of the text; selective listening (the learner perceives only some fragmentary elements of the text).

Listening strategy is, in fact, a nomenclature of strategies of foreign language speech reception and skills that presuppose it - all that is necessary to develop in the learner according to the requirements of the programme of a non-language university.

Speaking of listening strategy, we can perceive it as a mechanism for achieving the goal of oral speech perception, which is chosen consciously, meaningfully and deliberately and realised on the basis of combining the learner's knowledge and skills. This means that the student sets a goal and designates ways and means of achieving this goal, relying on his/her own abilities and possibilities with the help of knowledge and skills. This is how the aspect of plannedness is realised.

Conscientiousness means that the learner has a meaningful approach to the learning process, as it is determined by the personal choice of the student, who is responsible for the success of this process. This implies and conditions independence and autonomy within the learning process, i.e. the student ceases to be an object,

but becomes a subject of learning. In accordance with the learning material, the student is aware of his/her actions and analyses their results in accordance with the motivations and learning objectives.

With regard to the intentionality of applying strategies, it is important to mention the rational approach of the student, who decides on the possibility or necessity of certain rational mechanisms of activity, having an intention, a disposition to implement the action in accordance with the intended programme to obtain the result. Consequently, strategies are, in fact, ways and methods coming from the student himself, demonstrating his autonomy, the personal nature of the process of audio information retrieval, increasing motivation, which is a product of the student's learning and life needs.

For the implementation of listening strategy it is necessary to execute an individual mental plan, which reflects the way of information retrieval through the students' definition of the purpose of listening, their performance of actions to use and combine the assigned knowledge, skills and abilities of listening comprehension and reflection of their activity. Thus, the components of the strategy of meaningful listening are goal setting, planning, conscious activity to implement the plan (with the help of knowledge, skills, abilities, the ability to select and combine them), awareness of the result of the activity.

However, to form a strategy of listening comprehension does not mean to master a set of skills. Since the conditions under which communication and listening to an oral message take place are never fully repeated, the listener has to use a variety of skills, but in different combinations and sequences. So, the application of strategy in the listening process is individual and creative. To implement a strategy means to choose a way of extracting information in such a way that the oral speech can be perceived in different situations in order to achieve the goal of listening comprehension. Teaching the use of strategies demonstrates an individualised approach to the learner in the learning process, as the strategy is personally assigned to each learner and he/she combines skills during listening so that they function as a unified system.

References

1. <https://learningcenter.unc.edu/tips-and-tools/academic-listening-strategies/>
2. <https://ofmouthandmind-slp.com/how-to-teach-listening-comprehension-strategies-for-better-results/>
3. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-importance-of-improving-listening-skills-at-non-linguistic-faculties-of-universities>
4. <https://oxfordtefl.com/blog/8-techniques-to-teach-advanced-listening-skills-in-the-elt-classroom/>